

1 **Theoretical and empirical comparisons of expected**
2 **and realized relationships for the X-chromosome**

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1 **Abstract**

2 **Background**

3 X-chromosomal loci present different inheritance patterns compared to autosomal loci and
4 must be modeled accordingly. Sexual chromosomes are not systematically considered in
5 whole-genome relationship matrices although rules based on genealogical or marker
6 information have been derived. Loci on the X-chromosome could have a significant
7 contribution to the additive genetic variance, in particular for some traits such as those related
8 to reproduction. Accounting for the X-chromosome relationship matrix might thus be
9 informative to better understand the architecture of complex traits (e.g., by estimating the
10 variance associated to this chromosome) and to improve their genomic prediction. For such
11 applications, previous studies have shown the benefits of combining information from
12 genotyped and ungenotyped individuals.

13 **Results**

14 In this paper, we start by presenting rules to compute a genomic relationship matrix (GRM)
15 for the X-chromosome (\mathbf{G}^X) without making any assumption on dosage compensation, and
16 based on coding of gene content with 0/1 for males and 0/1/2 for females. This coding adjusts
17 naturally to previously derived pedigree-based relationships (\mathbf{S}) for the X-chromosome. When
18 needed, we propose to accommodate and estimate dosage compensation and genetic
19 heterogeneity across sexes via multiple trait models. Using a Holstein dairy cattle dataset,
20 including males and females, we then empirically illustrate that realized relationships (\mathbf{G}^X)
21 matches expectations (\mathbf{S}). However, \mathbf{G}^X presents high deviations from \mathbf{S} . \mathbf{G}^X has also a lower
22 dimensionality compared to the autosomal GRM. In particular, individuals are frequently
23 identical along the entire chromosome. Finally, we confirm that the heritability of gene
24 content for markers on the X-chromosome that are estimated by using \mathbf{S} is 1, further

1 demonstrating that \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{G}^X can be combined. For the pseudo-autosomal region, we
2 demonstrate that the expected relationships vary according to position as a result of the sex-
3 gradient. We end by presenting the rules to construct the ' \mathbf{H} matrix' by combining both
4 relationship matrices.

5 **Conclusions**

6 This work shows theoretically and empirically that a pedigree-based relationship matrix built
7 with rules specifically developed for the X-chromosome (\mathbf{S}) matches the realized GRM for
8 the X-chromosome. Therefore, applications that combine expected relationships and
9 genotypes for markers on the X-chromosome should use \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{G}^X .

10 **Background**

11 Additive relationships and the associated matrices are important in essential applications such
12 as estimation of the heritability of a complex trait, prediction of genomic values or inference
13 of unknown relationships (e.g., in wild populations). The additive relationships can be
14 estimated from pedigree data when the genealogy is available as in many livestock species.
15 Alternatively, they can be inferred from genotypes at a set of markers. This requires the
16 genotyping of the individuals but provides realized relationships contrary to pedigree-based
17 estimators that are expected values. More accurate predictions are obtained when using
18 genomic information. In addition, such genomic relationships are not affected by pedigree
19 errors and can even be obtained without pedigrees. For these reasons, genomic relationships
20 are superior to pedigree-based values, e.g. [1]. When only a subset of individuals is genotyped
21 and the genealogy is available for other individuals, it might be advantageous to combine both
22 relationship matrices [2]. This is, for instance, the core of single-step genomic best linear
23 unbiased prediction (SSGBLUP) that results in higher prediction accuracies than GBLUP [2,
24 3]. The same strategy has also been applied in genome-wide association studies (GWAS), e.g.

1 [4]. However, both approaches require that the genomic relationship is scaled appropriately.
2 The X-chromosome has often been ignored [5], and is still not systematically used (but see [6,
3 7]), in quantitative genetics applications (genetic or genomic predictions, GWAS) although it
4 might have important contributions to the genetic variance since it is one of the longest
5 chromosomes (in cattle) and this chromosome is gene rich [7–9]. The contribution of the X-
6 chromosome to phenotypic variation might be important for fertility or reproduction traits,
7 e.g. [10–12]. Examples include variants that affect litter size in sheep, e.g. [13], infertility in
8 cattle [14], or bull fertility [11]. More generally, quantitative trait loci (QTL) on the X-
9 chromosome have been reported in previous studies, e.g. [15], which indicates that this
10 chromosome should be taken into account.

11 Fernando and Grossman [16] presented the rules to construct the X-chromosome relationship
12 matrix **S** and its inverse from pedigree records, in a proper quantitative genetics framework.
13 Contrary to popular belief, this matrix is quite different from its autosomal counterpart **A** (the
14 “numerator relationship matrix”). Two important differences are that the diagonal values of **S**
15 for males are always 0.5, and that there is no relationship between a male and its sire. For
16 instance, the correlation of the off-diagonal elements of **A** and **S** across the last five
17 generations (with complete pedigree tracing back to 40 generations) of line A in Fernandez et
18 al. [17] is 0.79 across all females but only 0.36 across males (own calculation, results not
19 shown). Still, in the pre-genomic era, relationships at the X-chromosome have been basically
20 ignored.

21 In genomic analyses, the X-chromosome presents some specific challenges such as more
22 complex inheritance patterns, lower quality of the genome assembly, lower genotype quality
23 (lower call rate) and fewer markers on the arrays (see [5]). Rules to construct the genomic
24 relationship matrix (GRM) have been proposed [7, 18] but they impose hypotheses such as

1 the presence or absence of dosage compensation, yet dosage compensation varies across traits
2 and tissues [8]. Although dosage compensation is not relevant for sex-specific traits such as
3 milk or egg production, it should be estimated when the setting allows it (e.g., for phenotypes
4 expressed in both sexes). In this paper, we illustrate that this can be achieved in a multiple
5 trait setting. Then, we show that gene content for markers on the X-chromosome can be
6 considered as a quantitative trait of heritability 1, naturally leading to applications that
7 combine expected and realized relationships such as the single-step methods. We also provide
8 rules to construct an **H** matrix for the X-chromosome combining genotyped and ungenotyped
9 animals, either with metafounders or not.

10 Subsequently, we use real cattle data to verify whether the proposed pedigree-based and
11 genomic relationships for the X-chromosome have similar expectations. In particular, we
12 illustrate that genomic relationships are close to the expected values, and that the strong
13 associated variation is due to the smaller size of the X-chromosome compared to all the
14 autosomes considered together. To further illustrate the equivalence between the two
15 relationship matrices, we estimate the heritability of the gene content [19] of markers located
16 on the X-chromosome, and we show that it works as expected – heritability of gene content is
17 equal to 1 when using pedigree relationships for markers on the X-chromosome, but is lower
18 when using pedigree relationships for autosomal loci, because the latter does not describe
19 correctly relationships for the X-chromosome.

20 Overall, this work shows theoretically and empirically that **S** matches the realized GRM on
21 the X-chromosome. This allows extension of applications that combine expected relationships
22 and genotypes to markers on the X-chromosome.

23 **Theory**

1 Here we briefly review the current theory for pedigree-based relationships [16] and marker-
2 based relationships [7, 18] and suggest some extensions. We want to present a theory for the
3 X-chromosome that, by construction, is compatible with existing pedigree-based methods. In
4 general (unless explicitly mentioned), we will refer to the X-specific part. When we refer to
5 the pseudo-autosomal region (PAR), we will use the abbreviation PAR. Our presentation will
6 focus on mammals but concepts can be easily translated to birds reversing the sexes.

7 **Theory at a single-locus**

8 Fernando and Grossman [16] derived rules to estimate a pedigree-based genetic relationship
9 matrix (\mathbf{S}) for the X-chromosome. For a biallelic locus (e.g., A/B), males carry a single copy
10 (coming from their dam) whereas females carry two copies (coming from their sire and dam).
11 In their model, allelic effects were identical in males and females. This corresponds to define
12 the effects of loci in terms of expected differences across female descendants, but also to
13 absence of dosage compensation (see definition below). Nevertheless, this relationship matrix
14 can be rescaled to account for different levels of dosage compensation. As a result, it can be
15 used for all traits and genetic architectures. Defining effects in female descendants is
16 convenient as these represent an adequate reference population to define additive genotypic
17 values and receive gametes from both their sire and dam. In addition, Fernando and Grossman
18 [16] assumed no imprinting - this means that females receiving alleles A and B (from the sire
19 and dam, respectively) will have the same genotypic value than females receiving alleles B
20 and A (from the sire and dam, respectively). In this paper, we followed their hypotheses,
21 including the absence of imprinting. By doing this, genomic and pedigree-based relationships
22 will be compatible and coherent.

23 For a biallelic locus on the X-chromosome, numerical coding as gene content may proceed as
24 $\{0,1\}$ for males (say, for genotypes $\{A,B\}$) and $\{0,1,2\}$ for females (say, for genotypes

1 {AA,AB,BB}). This coding is consistent with the theory of Fernando and Grossman [16], and
 2 corresponds to the number of biological copies in males (that are hemizygotes). Note that
 3 equivalent GRM can be obtained using the {0,2} coding for males, proposed for instance by
 4 Su et al. [7], combined with appropriate scaling factors.

5 Imagine the generation n constituted by females (our reference population); sires from
 6 generation n-1 have genotypes either A or B. Because sires are haploids, their respective
 7 additive genotypic values (measured as expected progeny differences in females) are either
 8 $u = (1 - p)\alpha$ or $u = -p\alpha$ where $p = freq(A)$, $q = freq(B)$ and α is the substitution effect
 9 of “A” in the female offspring. This is the reason we code gene content as {1,0} (for
 10 genotypes A and B, respectively) as proposed above. Accordingly, variance for gene content
 11 in males is pq whereas variance for gene content in females is $2pq$.

12 For a given locus, gene content from all individuals can be summarized by a vector \mathbf{m}^X
 13 (hereafter, X refers to the X-chromosome) that contains the number of copies of the reference
 14 allele, {0,1} for males and {0,1,2} for females. The gene content at all loci can be encoded in
 15 a matrix \mathbf{M}^X , with columns \mathbf{m}_j^X that contain the gene dosage at locus j , and elements $M_{i,j}^X$
 16 corresponding to the gene content of individual i at that locus.

17 Genomic relationships for the X-chromosome

18 From the above, and extending the reasoning to several marker effects in vector α , the
 19 additive genotypic value of individual i in a female population would be $u_i = \mathbf{M}_{[i,]}^X \alpha -$
 20 $E(\mathbf{M}_{[i,]}^X \alpha)$ where $\mathbf{M}_{[i,]}^X$ is the i -th row in matrix \mathbf{M}^X . Then, we have:

$$21 \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{males} \\ \mathbf{u}_{females} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{males}^X - \mathbf{1p}' \\ \mathbf{M}_{females}^X - \mathbf{2p}' \end{pmatrix} \alpha = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{Z}_{males}^X \\ \mathbf{Z}_{females}^X \end{pmatrix} \alpha = \mathbf{Z}^X \alpha.$$

1 Note that the notion of dosage compensation does not intervene here because the male
 2 additive genotypic values are expressed on the trait in the female population. Using $\sigma_u^2 =$
 3 $2\sum p_i q_i \sigma_\alpha^2$ (in other words, we refer relationships to genetic variance in an ideal female
 4 population) we obtain:

$$5 \text{Var} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{males} \\ \mathbf{u}_{females} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{\sigma_u^2}{2\sum p_i q_i} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{males}^X - \mathbf{1p}' \\ \mathbf{M}_{females}^X - \mathbf{2p}' \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{males}^X - \mathbf{1p}' \\ \mathbf{M}_{females}^X - \mathbf{2p}' \end{pmatrix}' = \frac{\mathbf{Z}^X \mathbf{Z}^{X'}}{2\sum p_i q_i} \sigma_u^2 = \mathbf{G}^X \sigma_u^2.$$

6 This is almost identical to the treatment of the chromosome X in Yang et al. [18] but we do
 7 not use standardized genotypes. This is also similar, but not identical, to VanRaden's [20] \mathbf{G}
 8 for autosomes. The differences between \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{G}^X are that, in the latter, males are coded as
 9 $\{0,1\}$ and centered by p , not by $2p$, and the denominator refers to the genetic variance of a
 10 female population. The most important difference, that is not obvious in this matrix
 11 formulation, is that gene content for markers on the X-chromosome does not behave like gene
 12 content for markers on autosomes, even in females, because the paternal copy comes from the
 13 sire with no possibility of Mendelian sampling or recombination. This has implications that
 14 we will see later.

15 *Some properties of the X-chromosome genomic relationship matrix*

16 In a population with allele frequencies p , the average value of the diagonal elements of \mathbf{G}^X is,
 17 as expected, 0.5 for males, but there are deviations from this value. By definition, there are no
 18 deviations from Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium or inbreeding in the male population, because
 19 there are no diploids – only haploids. Consider the diagonal elements $G_{i,i}^X = \frac{1}{W} \sum (M_{i,j}^X - p_j)^2$,
 20 $W = 2\sum p_j q_j$. In a population, for a given locus j , there is a proportion p of males with
 21 genotypes $M_{i,j}^X = 1$ and a proportion $1-p$ with genotypes $M_{i,j}^X = 0$. Weighting each square
 22 term by its probabilities, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
1 \quad E(G_{i,i}^X) &= \frac{1}{W} \sum [(1 - p_j)^2 p_j + (0 - p_j)^2 (1 - p_j)] \\
2 \quad &= \frac{1}{W} \sum [q_j^2 p_j + p_j^2 q_j] = \frac{1}{W} \sum [(q_j + p_j) q_j p_j] = \frac{1}{W} \sum p_j q_j = 0.5.
\end{aligned}$$

3 However, there are individual variations around this value, e.g. if some animals carry rare
4 alleles. Using analogous arguments, it can be shown that the average value for females is 1,
5 and that averages of \mathbf{G}^X for a population of males, females, or both, are 0. Elements of \mathbf{G}^X are
6 comparable to pedigree relationships in \mathbf{S} (Fernando and Grossman [16]) only if base-
7 population allele frequencies are used. Otherwise, the matrix is biased (generally,
8 relationships are underestimated) and corrections are needed.

9 One manner to create a \mathbf{G}^X matrix that, by default, is compatible with \mathbf{S} is to use the
10 metafounders theory [21], using $p = 0.5$ to construct \mathbf{G}^X and using a pedigree-relationship
11 matrix constructed with metafounders, \mathbf{S}^Y (rules and code for this matrix and its inverse are in
12 Additional file 1). In this method, because allele frequencies are set to 0.5, the diagonal values
13 of \mathbf{G}^X for males are 0.5 by construction. Note that, in the application realized on real data, we
14 will not use that approach and will use estimated allele frequencies.

15 Now we consider the rank of \mathbf{G}^X . The rank of $\mathbf{G}^X = \frac{\mathbf{Z}^X \mathbf{Z}^{X'}}{2 \sum p_i q_i}$ is the row rank of \mathbf{Z}^X , in other
16 words, the number of linearly independent rows. For instance, a male that receives its X-
17 chromosome from its maternal grandsire without recombination (in its dam) results in a rank
18 reduction of 1. Because X-chromosomes are passed on from males to offspring without
19 recombination, and males only have one copy, this results in less “shuffling” of loci across the
20 chromosome and therefore in higher linkage disequilibrium (LD). Thus, the row rank of \mathbf{Z}^X
21 and the rank of \mathbf{G}^X are likely lower than the row rank of an autosomal chromosome of the
22 same size, such as, for instance, bovine chromosome 2. This will be numerically evaluated

1 later in this work.

2 **Treatment of dosage compensation and sex heterogeneity in traits expressed in** 3 **both sexes**

4 Many traits in livestock are expressed only in one sex (e.g., milk production), but some (e.g.,
5 growth) are expressed in both sexes. However, as for autosomes, the genetic correlation
6 between sexes is not necessarily 1 [22]. Dosage compensation is a mechanism that balances
7 gene expression differences in X-linked genes between sexes, e.g., [5]. This can be
8 accomplished by randomly silencing one of the copies in females on the X-chromosome,
9 often referred to as X-chromosome inactivation [5]. However, apart from X-inactivation,
10 other mechanisms exist that achieve dosage compensation such as a two-fold increase of
11 expression in males or halving both copies in females [see review by 8]. This phenomenon
12 might explain why in spite of carrying only one copy of the X-chromosome, males present as
13 much genetic variation *in their* phenotypes associated with variants from the X-chromosome
14 as females (see for instance in [23]). Yang et al. [18] and Su et al. [7] presented three models
15 that differ on the assumption of dosage compensation (none, full compensation (same
16 genotypic mean), and same genotypic variance in males and females). This allows
17 construction of a GRM for the X-chromosome, but at the price of assuming a certain factor k
18 of dosage compensation that needs to be known or assumed. Below, we present a general
19 alternative strategy, including explicit estimation of dosage compensation. To summarize, for
20 a trait expressed in both sexes, we propose a multiple-trait model (phenotypes in both sexes
21 are considered as two different traits). Ideally, this bivariate approach should be applied to
22 model genetic effects that are associated with the autosomes too, although here we focus on
23 genetic effects associated with the X-chromosome. If the genetic correlation across sexes is 1,
24 then the dosage compensation is a function of the covariances, \mathbf{G}^X can be explicitly built
25 including dosage compensation, and a single-trait model is possible as described below.

1 ***SNP-BLUP with variable dosage compensation***

2 Considering (random) marker effects α , that are expressed in terms of effects in the female
 3 population, then the genotypic value () of own performance of males is $\mathbf{g}_{males} = k\mathbf{M}^X\alpha$ and
 4 that of own performance of females $\mathbf{g}_{females} = \mathbf{M}^X\alpha$, where k allows for effects to scale
 5 differently between sexes as a result of dosage compensation for instance.

6 In other words, scalar k considers the dosage compensation and is not bounded to predefined
 7 values. For instance, the three hypotheses of Yang et al. [18] would be modelled as: no dosage
 8 compensation ($k = 1$), full dosage compensation ($k = 2$), which results in the same mean but
 9 a doubling of the genotypic variance in males compared to females), and the same genotypic
 10 variance ($k = \sqrt{2}$) (but a different mean). However, other values of k are possible or even
 11 likely [8].

12 In practice, both α and k need to be estimated from data. For this, we propose an equivalent
 13 multiple-trait based model where k becomes a covariance component, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 14 \quad \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{males} \\ \mathbf{y}_{females} \end{pmatrix} &= \dots \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{g}_{males} \\ \mathbf{g}_{females} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{males} \\ \mathbf{e}_{females} \end{pmatrix} \\
 15 \quad &= \dots + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{M}_{males}^X \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} \alpha^{(males)} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{M}_{females}^X \end{pmatrix} \alpha + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_{males} \\ \mathbf{e}_{females} \end{pmatrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

16 Where we keep α for females. With associated distribution:

$$17 \quad Var \begin{pmatrix} \alpha^{(males)} \\ \alpha \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{\alpha-m}^2 & \sigma_{\alpha-m,f} \\ \sigma_{\alpha-m,f} & \sigma_{\alpha-f}^2 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{I}.$$

18 This model considers dosage compensation but also different effects of the same alleles in
 19 males and females, i.e. genetic correlation different from 1, e.g. [22]. In this model, variance
 20 components might be estimated, i.e. by REML. If the correlation of α effects across

1 phenotypes of males and females is 1, then $\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{\alpha-m}^2 & \sigma_{\alpha-m,f} \\ \sigma_{\alpha-m,f} & \sigma_{\alpha-f}^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} k^2 \sigma_{\alpha}^2 & k \sigma_{\alpha}^2 \\ k \sigma_{\alpha}^2 & \sigma_{\alpha}^2 \end{pmatrix}$. Thus, it is
2 possible to check simultaneously if the genetic architecture is the same and (if it is the same,
3 i.e. the correlation is 1) the extent of dosage compensation. Obviously, the same two-trait
4 model (one per sex) should be run simultaneously for the autosomes and the X-chromosome
5 to check the heterogeneity of the trait across sexes. If the genetic correlation is already known
6 to be 1 (or if it is assumed to be 1), k might be estimated with a more parsimonious univariate
7 model accounting for heterogeneous variance.

8 ***Genomic BLUP for the X-chromosome with variable dosage compensation***

9 Let us now consider genetic evaluation in a GBLUP form for own phenotype. As before, to
10 take dosage compensation into account, we can consider a multiple-trait model equivalent to
11 the SNP-BLUP presented before:

$$12 \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{y}_{males} \\ \mathbf{y}_{females} \end{pmatrix} = \dots + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{males} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{u}_{females} \end{pmatrix} + \mathbf{e},$$

$$13 \text{ with } Var \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{u}_{males} \\ \mathbf{u}_{females} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{u-m}^2 & \sigma_{u-m,f} \\ \sigma_{u-m,f} & \sigma_{u-f}^2 \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{G}^X.$$

14 Again, the analysis should model multiple traits for both autosomes and the X-chromosome.

15 The respective genetic variances (assuming Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium) are $\sigma_{u-males}^2 =$

$$16 k^2 \sum p_i q_i \left(\alpha_i^{(males)} \right)^2 \text{ and } \sigma_{u-females}^2 = 2 \sum p_i q_i \alpha_i^2.$$

$$17 \text{ If the genetic correlation across sexes is 1, we have } \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{u-males}^2 & \sigma_{u-m,f} \\ \sigma_{u-m,f} & \sigma_u^2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{k^2}{2} \sigma_u^2 & \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}} \sigma_u^2 \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}} \sigma_u^2 & \sigma_u^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

18 from which k can be solved. The factor $\frac{k^2}{2}$ is explained because males have half the number of

19 copies compared to females but effects are scaled by k . It is then possible to define a new \mathbf{G}^X

1 explicitly accounting for the level of dosage compensation, and that can be used in single-trait
 2 analyses:

$$3 \mathbf{G}^X = \frac{1}{2\sum p_i q_i} \begin{pmatrix} k\mathbf{M}_{males}^X - k\mathbf{1p}' \\ \mathbf{M}_{females}^X - \mathbf{2p}' \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} k\mathbf{M}_{males}^X - k\mathbf{1p}' \\ \mathbf{M}_{females}^X - \mathbf{2p}' \end{pmatrix}'.$$

4 The different matrices in Yang et al. [18] are particular cases of this GRM, setting $k = 1, \sqrt{2}$
 5 or 2. As for the SNP-BLUP, more parsimonious univariate models are possible to account for
 6 heterogeneity of variances across sexes when the genetic correlation is known to be 1.

7 As already mentioned, an equivalent GRM can be obtained when coding males as {0,2} by
 8 using appropriate scaling factors. This coding is commonly used in dairy cattle genetics [6, 7],
 9 and amounts to assume $k = 2$. More importantly, for sex-specific traits (observed in a single
 10 sex) such as milk and egg production, the value of k (or the choice of coding) is irrelevant.

11 **Genomic applications combining pedigree relationships and genotypes on the** 12 **X-chromosome**

13 *Heritability of gene content and single step*

14 Fernando and Grossman [16] described the pedigree-based relationship matrix \mathbf{S} (and its
 15 sparse inverse \mathbf{S}^{-1}) at a random locus on chromosome X. Seen as a quantitative trait, the
 16 methods that we presented fit their modelling of gene content in the males as {0,1} and in
 17 females as {0,1,2}.

18 There are two major applications of pedigree relationships to the use of genotypes from
 19 markers on the X-chromosome. First, consider modelling gene content m as a quantitative
 20 trait [24, 25]. Variance and covariances of m across individuals are described by matrix \mathbf{S} :

$$21 E \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{m}_{males} \\ \mathbf{m}_{females} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{1p} \\ \mathbf{2p} \end{pmatrix}; \text{Var} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{m}_{males} \\ \mathbf{m}_{females} \end{pmatrix} = \mathbf{S}2pq.$$

1 For instance, it is possible to estimate the heritability of gene content for quality control
 2 purposes [19].

3 Second, we can also predict gene content from ungenotyped individuals thanks to genotyped
 4 individuals using the pedigree-based matrix \mathbf{S} . The individuals in the pedigree file can be split
 5 into genotyped (subscript 2) and ungenotyped (subscript 1) individuals, and the $\mathbf{S} =$

6 $\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{S}_{11} & \mathbf{S}_{12} \\ \mathbf{S}_{21} & \mathbf{S}_{22} \end{pmatrix}$ matrix partitioned accordingly. We will work with centered gene content, i.e.

7 $\mathbf{Z}^X = \mathbf{M}^X - \mathbf{1}\mathbf{p}'$ for males and $\mathbf{Z}^X = \mathbf{M}^X - \mathbf{2}\mathbf{p}'$ for females. At a single locus, the linear

8 prediction of \mathbf{z}_1^X for ungenotyped individuals from observed genotypes (\mathbf{z}_2^X) in genotyped

9 individuals is $\widehat{\mathbf{z}}_1^X = E(\mathbf{z}_1^X | \mathbf{z}_2^X) = \mathbf{S}_{12}\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{z}_2^X$ with associated variance (assuming multivariate

10 normality) $var(\mathbf{z}_1^X | \mathbf{z}_2^X) = (\mathbf{S}_{11} - \mathbf{S}_{12}\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{S}_{21})2pq$. This allows the construction of the

11 SSGBLUP relationship matrix \mathbf{H}^X including the X-chromosome as described next. The

12 relationship matrix is built as a cross-product of estimated and observed \mathbf{Z}^X , considering the

13 error in the estimation (see Christensen and Lund [3] for the details), which yields a

14 SSGBLUP type matrix:

15
$$\mathbf{H}^X = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{S}_{11} - \mathbf{S}_{12}\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{S}_{21} + \mathbf{S}_{12}\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{G}^X\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{S}_{21} & \mathbf{S}_{12}\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{G}^X \\ \mathbf{G}^X\mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1}\mathbf{S}_{21} & \mathbf{G}^X \end{pmatrix},$$

16 with the inverse, assuming invertible \mathbf{G}_X^{-1} :

17
$$(\mathbf{H}^X)^{-1} = \mathbf{S}^{-1} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \mathbf{G}_X^{-1} - \mathbf{S}_{22}^{-1} \end{pmatrix}.$$

18 It is also possible to develop a so-called single step SNP-BLUP [26] to work directly with
 19 effects of markers on the X-chromosome instead of additive genotypic values.

20 The development above needs base allele frequencies to construct \mathbf{Z}_2^X and fit \mathbf{H}^X to the

1 pedigree base. If these are not available, an option is to analytically integrate (unknown) base
2 allele frequencies [27] which in practice means to use $p = 0.5$ across all loci for the
3 construction of \mathbf{G}^X and use the metafounder's theory to construct \mathbf{S} . This is described in
4 Additional file 1.

5 Note that if a different coding of gene content is applied, similar applications can be
6 performed by rescaling \mathbf{S} . Indeed, if $\{0,1,2\}$ coding is chosen for females and any coding
7 $\{0,k\}$ is chosen for males to construct a particular \mathbf{G}^X , then \mathbf{S} can be rescaled appropriately by
8 multiplying the (male, male) part by k^2 and the (male, female) and (female, male) parts by k .
9 Rescaling \mathbf{S} might be more convenient than recoding genotypes in already existing databases.

10 **Note on combining pedigree relationships and genotypes for markers in the** 11 **pseudo-autosomal region**

12 The PAR that behaves differently than the X-chromosome specific part represents a much
13 smaller region (approximately 5 Mb) and is hence less likely to have an important
14 contribution to genetic variation. The PAR has also much larger recombination rate in males,
15 e.g. [28, 29, 30]. The rules to estimate the GRM are the same as for the autosomes and the
16 SNPs from the PAR do not need specific rules. However, the expected relationships are not
17 the same as for the autosomes. Indeed, there is a so-called sex-gradient in the PAR [28]
18 because sires transmit more often their paternal haplotype (associated with the Y-
19 chromosome) to their sons and their maternal haplotype (associated with the X-specific part)
20 to their daughters. This probability is equal to $(1-r)$, where r is the genetic distance to the
21 pseudo-autosomal boundary (PAB) in males. Therefore, the allelic effects (or eventually the
22 gene content) of son mo and daughter fo from sire s are:

$$23 \quad v_{mo}^p = (1-r)v_s^p + rv_s^m + \varepsilon_{mo}^p,$$

$$1 \quad v_{fo}^p = (1 - r)v_s^p + rv_s^m + \varepsilon_{fo}^p,$$

2 where superscript p and m indicates paternal and maternal alleles, subscripts mo and fo
3 indicate male and female offspring, subscript s refers to the sire and ε represents residual
4 effects (due to sampling). These equations are similar to those that describe the transmission
5 of a QTL from parent to offspring conditionally on a set of markers proposed by Fernando
6 and Grossman [31]. In that case, the probability of inheritance of a paternal and maternal
7 allele is estimated based on the markers. Here, the sex of the offspring plays the role of a
8 marker located at the PAB. Note that for dams, there is no such gradient and transmission has
9 equal probability as on autosomes:

$$10 \quad v_{mo}^m = 0.5v_d^p + 0.5v_d^m + \varepsilon_{mo}^m,$$

$$11 \quad v_{fo}^m = 0.5v_d^p + 0.5v_d^m + \varepsilon_{fo}^m,$$

12 where subscript d stands for dam. These equations correspond to standard pedigree-based
13 expectations. The expected relationship matrix is different for each marker on the PAR as it
14 depends on its position. It can be estimated using the genetic distance from the PAB
15 (measured in males), the above equations and the rules described in Fernando and Grossman
16 [31]. Hereafter this matrix will be noted \mathbf{P}^r where r is the distance (in cM). Rules were also
17 provided to compute directly the inverse of this relationship matrix [31].

18 **Application**

19 **Empirical comparison of pedigree-based and genomic relationships for** 20 **markers on the X-chromosome**

21 *Data*

22 The dataset used in our study consisted in a sample of 6085 French Holstein individuals

1 genotyped with the BovineSNP50 or the BovineHD genotyping arrays (Illumina, San Diego,
2 CA). These 637 sires and 5448 dams corresponded to the French Holstein parents that have a
3 phenotype for global recombination rate in the study by Kadri et al. [32]. For the autosomes,
4 we conserved the 30,127 markers selected by Kadri et al. [32] after discarding monomorphic
5 markers or those with a low call rate (lower than 0.95), markers that deviated from Hardy-
6 Weinberg proportions, that had more than 10 Mendelian inconsistencies or were associated
7 with putative map errors. Similar filtering rules were applied to a set of 853 SNPs mapping to
8 the X-chromosome in the ARS-UCD1.2 bovine assembly and common to the two genotyping
9 arrays (see also [30]). The X-specific part ended at the PAB, set at position 133,300,518 [9].
10 X-specific markers with an average homozygosity lower than 0.98 in males were also filtered
11 out, leaving 744 SNPs on the X-specific part and 73 SNPs on the PAR. Remaining Mendelian
12 inconsistencies were subsequently erased. The pedigree including available ancestors
13 contained 16,669 individuals; the oldest ancestors from each genotyped individual traced back
14 to 7 to 16 generations in males and 9 to 17 generations in females. These genotyped males
15 and females had more than, respectively, 90 and 95% known ancestors in the fourth pedigree
16 generation.

17 We used LINKPHASE3 [33] to reconstruct haplotypes of genotyped animals, to estimate the
18 probability of transmission of parental haplotypes to offspring at each marker position and to
19 obtain the number of cross-overs on the X-specific part in female meiosis.

20 **Comparison of genetic relationship matrices**

21 Pedigree-based relationship matrices were estimated with our own code. For the autosomes
22 (**A**), we used the tabular method [34] whereas for the sex-chromosome (**S**) we used the rules
23 described in Fernando and Grossman [16]. The genomic relationship matrices (GRM) for
24 autosomes (**G**) and the sex-chromosome (**G^X**) were computed with GCTA [18] using the first

1 model proposed by VanRaden [20] and assuming equal variance of SNP effects. More
2 specifically, for the X-chromosome (X-GRM), we used the coding {0,1} for males and
3 {0,1,2} for females and then the cross-product $\mathbf{G}^X = \frac{\mathbf{z}^X \mathbf{z}^{X'}}{2 \sum pq}$ as described in theory and using
4 the allele frequencies estimated in the sample, which underestimates a little the relationships
5 compared to pedigree-based relationships. If this relationship matrix is used in a single-trait
6 GBLUP analysis (for instance to analyze growth), multiple-trait analyses should be used to
7 consider dosage compensation as presented in the section 'Theory'. We estimated one GRM
8 for all autosomes jointly and also one for chromosome 2 (\mathbf{G}^{BTA2}), with a physical length
9 similar to the X-chromosome.

10 We started by comparing estimated relationships for different pairs of individuals (e.g., sire-
11 son, full-sisters, paternal half-brothers, etc.). We also rescaled expected relationships in terms
12 of correlations between animals [35]. This amounts to dividing relationships between i and j
13 by the square root of the product from the diagonal elements i and j (on autosomes, this
14 correlation between genetic effects is equal to the additive relationship in absence of
15 inbreeding). This rescaling makes the relationships less dependent to variation in diagonal
16 elements and ensures that the values are between -1 and 1, making them more easy to
17 interpret. Subsequently, we estimated the correlations between pedigree-based and genomic
18 relationships for all elements or for off-diagonal elements only. Finally, we compared the
19 dimensionality of the different relationship matrices by performing a singular value
20 decomposition (SVD). First, we estimated the percentage of the overall variance explained by
21 the i -th pair of SVD vectors (called the i -th SVD mode) as:

$$22 \quad \frac{sv_i^2}{\sum sv_j^2},$$

1 where sv_j are the singular values. Subsequently, we estimated the percentage variance
2 captured by the k largest singular values and determined the values of k needed to capture 90,
3 95 or 99% of variance.

4 ***Heritability of gene content***

5 Forneris et al. [19] proposed to estimate the heritability of gene content to perform quality
6 control of genotypes. Here, we estimated heritability of gene content for the 744 markers on
7 the X-chromosome (X-specific part) by using either the autosomal additive relationship
8 matrix **A**, or the X-chromosome relationship matrix **S**. In both cases, the relationship matrices
9 were computed from pedigree data. The gene content was equal to the number of copies of the
10 reference alleles (ranging from 0 to 2 in females and 0 to 1 in males). Variance components
11 were estimated with the AI-REML algorithm implemented in the blupf90 package [36].
12 Comparisons allowed to check which relationship matrix (**S** or **A**) best fits the data, and at the
13 same time, whether covariances of gene content at a locus are correctly described by **S** as
14 expected (i.e., if the heritability estimate is 1, the theory fits the reality). First, the heritability
15 was estimated by including all animals. Most of the individuals were females (90%) and
16 meiosis is similar on the X-chromosome and the autosomes for these whereas males have a
17 more deviant pattern. Therefore, we also worked exclusively with males to obtain more
18 contrasted comparisons.

19 Finally, we also estimated heritability of gene content for markers on the PAR with a similar
20 approach. In addition, to **A** and **S**, we also estimated expected relationships at different
21 distances from the PAB (0.1, 5, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 cM) by combining the transmission
22 probabilities described in Methods and the rules from Fernando and Grossman [31] to
23 estimate \mathbf{P}^r .

1 **Results**

2 **Expected relationships for markers on the X-chromosome**

3 Examples of expected relationships on the X-chromosomes and on the autosomes are in Table
4 1, including in terms of correlations between individuals. Contrary to autosomes for which the
5 relationship does not depend on the sex of an individual, for the X-chromosome, parent and
6 offspring genders matter. For instance, sire-son pairs or paternal half-brothers (with unrelated
7 dams) have a null expected relationship. Conversely, correlations between additive genetic
8 effects from maternal half-brothers are expected to be higher than for autosomes. Similarly,
9 correlations between genetic effects from mother-son pairs (0.71) or from paternal half-sisters
10 (0.50) are higher than for autosomes (0.50 and 0.25, respectively). It should also be noted that
11 maternal half-brothers and full-brothers have the same expected relationship (0.25). More
12 generally, we observe that expectations vary according to the sex of the full-sibs or half-sibs
13 and according to the sex of the common parent for half-sib pairs.

14

15 Insert Table 1 here.

16

17 ***Pedigree-based and realized relationships in the French Holstein cattle data***

18 Expected (pedigree-based) and realized (marker-based) additive genetic relationships between
19 the 6085 French Holstein individuals were estimated. The estimated correlations between
20 polygenic effects for selected categories of individuals are in Table 2, for the X-chromosome,
21 for the 29 autosomes jointly, and for chromosome 2. We observe that the genomic
22 relationships obtained with genetic markers fit the pedigree-based expectations (genomic
23 relationships are a bit lower because observed, not base, allele frequencies were used),

1 although with some variability. The realized genomic relationships were clearly closer to the
2 expected relationships derived for the X-chromosome with the rules from Fernando and
3 Grossman [16] than to the expectations derived for the autosomes. The opposite was observed
4 for realized relationships on the autosomes (also [see Additional file 2 Tables S1, S2 and S3]
5 for more details on the distributions). To quantify these observations, we computed the
6 correlations between realized and expected relationships. These were equal to 0.52, 0.81 and
7 0.33 for the X-chromosome, the whole-genome (the 29 autosomes) or chromosome 2,
8 respectively. When using only the off-diagonal elements, these correlations were respectively
9 0.51, 0.79 and 0.31, and 0.40, 0.79 and 0.35 when considering males only. Correlations
10 between off-diagonal elements from **S** and **G** or from **A** and **G^X**, were as expected lower
11 (respectively, 0.63 and 0.42), which indicates that **S** fits **G^X** better and **A** fits **G** better (the
12 correlation between elements from **A** and **S** being equal to 0.76 in our dataset). The genetic
13 relationships for chromosome 2 presented the lowest correlations between expected and
14 realized values whereas they were highest for relationships obtained from genome-wide
15 markers (on all 29 autosomes). In Fig. 1, we plotted realized and expected relationships
16 expressed as the additive genetic correlations between animals as defined by Wright [35]. We
17 observed a high level of variation along the Y-axis for genomic relationships estimated with
18 markers on the X-chromosome.

19

20 Insert Table 2 here.

21

22 Insert Figure 1 here.

1

2 Many pairs of individuals had a high realized genomic correlation (> 0.90), which indicates
3 that their respective X-chromosomes were almost identical. This trend was observed for the
4 whole range of expected relationships; some pairs of individuals expected to have a null
5 relationship had identical X-chromosomes (see also Fig. 2). More than 1800 pairs of
6 individuals had such high genomic correlations and the values were higher than 0.99 for more
7 than 628 pairs (see Table 3). Such high correlations were rare when relationships were
8 estimated on chromosome 2 (5 pairs with a correlation higher than 0.99). Finally, such a
9 pattern is not observed on the whole-genome (only 2 identical individuals) which is expected
10 since the relationship is estimated on a larger number of independent chromosomes
11 (segregating separately during meiosis). Overall, the frequency of high genomic correlations
12 were 50 to 100 times higher on chromosome X than on chromosome 2 or even more when
13 compared to estimates computed with all the autosomes (see Table 3). The frequency of high
14 genomic correlations on the X-chromosome was approximately 10 times higher when
15 considering males only.

16 Several factors explain the large number of high genomic correlations between pairs of
17 individuals on the X-chromosome. First, males have only one copy of the X-chromosome and
18 require thus only one pair of chromosomes to be identical, whereas on chromosome 2, two
19 pairs of chromosomes need to be simultaneously identical. In addition, chromosomes are
20 transmitted without recombination from sires to daughters. On average, in our phased dataset
21 dams transmitted non-recombining X-chromosomes in 26.4% of their gametes (see also [30]).
22 As a result, two maternal half-brothers have a $\sim 0.5 \times 0.264^2$ probability of inheriting the
23 same chromosome (1/32). Similarly, a son and its maternal grand-sire have a 0.5×0.264
24 probability of inheriting the same chromosome (representing 1/8 of such pairs). Even females

1 have sometimes an increased probability of inheriting two IBD chromosomes. Two full-
2 sisters will automatically inherit the same paternal chromosome and have a 0.5×0.264^2
3 probability of inheriting the same maternal chromosome, e.g., resulting in the same
4 probability (1/32) than for two maternal half-brothers.

5

6 Insert Figure 2 here.

7

8 Genomic relationships for the X-chromosome seemed visually more variable than estimates
9 for chromosome 2 (Fig. 1), although genetic correlations between expected and realized
10 values were higher for the X-chromosome. These higher correlations might be because
11 expected values are spread across a broader range on the X-chromosome (for instance, some
12 relationship is expected at 0.75). Finally, to illustrate further the distribution of the
13 relationships obtained with different chromosomes, in Fig. 2, we plotted the distribution of
14 genomic correlations for three categories of individuals: sire and sons (representing the
15 selected individuals with a high contribution to genetic progress), full-sisters, and paternal
16 half-sisters (producing cows). In the three cases, average realized relations were, as expected,
17 different for the X-chromosome and were much less variable when using all the autosomes.
18 We also observed a huge variation for sire/sons relationships on the X-chromosome with
19 values equal to 1 for some pairs although the mean value was close to 0. In full-sisters and
20 half-sisters, the genomic correlations seemed more variable when they were estimated for
21 chromosome 2. Standard deviations were larger for \mathbf{G}^X for relationships between two males
22 and smaller for relationships between females [see Additional file 2 Table S1, S2 and S3].

1 **Dimensionality of genomic relationship matrices**

2 Because of this different behavior, the GRM for the X-chromosome \mathbf{G}^X has a reduced
3 dimensionality compared to the whole-genome GRM or to \mathbf{G}^{BTA2} (Table 3). For instance, the
4 number of singular values needed to capture 99% of the total GRM variance was equal to 53
5 for the X-chromosome, 85 for chromosome 2, and 793 for the autosomes. Thus, \mathbf{G} has a
6 higher dimensionality (roughly 10×) than \mathbf{G}^{BTA2} , which has a higher dimensionality (roughly
7 1.5× larger, in spite of being a chromosome of the same physical length) than \mathbf{G}^X . The
8 number of non-zero singular values was equal to 5921, 5693 and 6085 for the X-chromosome,
9 chromosome 2 and the autosomal GRM. Consequently, both GRM obtained for a single
10 chromosome were non-positive definite.

11

12 Insert Table 3 here.

13

14 **Heritability of gene content for markers on the X-chromosome (PAR** 15 **included)**

16 When the heritability of gene content for markers on the X-chromosome (X-specific part
17 only) was estimated on all animals (males and females, simultaneously), the values estimated
18 with \mathbf{S} were on average equal to 0.9997 and higher than 0.95 for the 543 selected SNPs with a
19 minor allele frequency higher than 0.05 (Fig. 3). When using \mathbf{A} , the average estimated
20 heritability dropped to 0.9045 and was systematically lower than the estimates obtained with
21 \mathbf{S} (from -0.0019 to -0.1791 and -0.0952 on average). Thus, the relationship matrix constructed
22 using the rules for the sex-chromosome [16] had a perfect fit with the “natural” gene contents
23 for markers on the X-chromosome. When the gene content was estimated on males only,

1 estimated heritabilities were lower and differences were more contrasted. More variation was
2 expected since fewer individuals were used (approximately 10%). With the rules derived for
3 the X-chromosome, 49 (155) estimates were lower than 0.95 (0.99) and the average was
4 0.985. Using **A**, heritability estimates deteriorated, with 541 SNPs that had a value lower 0.95.
5 In fact, only two SNPs with a MAF equal to 0.05 had a value higher than 0.95. The
6 heritabilities obtained with **S** were always higher (Fig. 3). Overall, the high heritabilities
7 obtained when using all the individuals indicate that pedigree-based relationships in **S**
8 describe properly the covariance of gene content across individuals, and therefore the
9 expected (**S**) and observed (\mathbf{G}^X) relationship matrices can be combined in a unique matrix, for
10 instance in the scope of a SSGBLUP. When gene dosage was coded as {0,2} in males (instead
11 of {0,1} as previously), the estimated heritabilities with **S** dropped as expected whereas those
12 obtained with **A** increased [see Additional file 3 Figure S1]. However, when only males were
13 considered, **A** performed poorly again indicating that this matrix badly describes gene content
14 on the X-chromosome, independently of coding strategy in males. Importantly, appropriate
15 rescaling of **S** (multiplying elements by 2 for each male involved in the relationship) resulted
16 in an average heritability of 0.9968 across SNPs.

17

18 Insert Figure 3 here.

19

20 For markers on the PAR (60 markers with a MAF higher than 0.05), we clearly observed that
21 the probability for sires to transmit their paternal or maternal haplotypes is a function of the
22 sex of their offspring and the genetic distance from the PAB (Fig. 4). At the PAB, sons
23 (daughters) inherited systematically the paternal (maternal) haplotype from the sires. At the

1 tip of the chromosome, the disequilibrium was less strong but still present. Conversely, dams
2 transmitted with equal probability their two haplotypes to both sons and daughters. As
3 expected, heritability of gene content estimated with **A** or **S** was low along the whole PAR
4 (Fig. 5). **S** performed best at the PAB and **A** at the other end of the PAR. When expectations
5 were estimated using the sex of the offspring as a marker and the genetic distance to the PAB
6 (see Methods), we clearly observed that relationships matrices estimated with a short genetic
7 distance fitted well the markers that were close to the PAB and poorly markers at the end of
8 the chromosome (Fig. 5). The opposite was true for relationships estimated with long genetic
9 distances from the PAB. Both relationships matrices behaved imperfectly for markers located
10 in the middle of the PAR. In that case, the use of intermediate genetic distances worked well.
11 This indicates that for markers on the PAR, the expected relationships vary according to the
12 distance to the PAR as we predicted. The optimal relationship matrix on the PAR could be the
13 average of all these matrices (one matrix estimated for each SNP position). An alternative
14 would be to use a matrix \mathbf{P}^r at a moderate distance (e.g., 20 cM) since it performed relatively
15 well for the entire PAR (Fig. 5). Our results also suggest that the heritability of gene content
16 could be used to estimate the genetic distances on the PAR, although other methods already
17 exist for that purpose e.g. [37].

18

19 Insert Figure 4 here.

20 Insert Figure 5 here.

21

22 **Combining G^X and **S** in a single matrix**

1 In our data, \mathbf{G}^X was non-positive definite. One strategy to bend \mathbf{G}^X would be to combine it
2 with \mathbf{S} . As an example, we used a linear regression to scale the values of the \mathbf{G}^X such that both
3 the average of the diagonal elements and the average from all the elements are identical to the
4 corresponding values from \mathbf{S} [38]. To that end, first, we equalized variances in males and
5 females (e.g., multiplying the male variance by 2). The value of the regression coefficient was
6 close to 1 (0.9466) and the intercept was equal to 0.0963. Then, we obtained a combined
7 GRM as $\mathbf{G}^{X*} = \alpha\mathbf{S} + \beta\mathbf{G}^X$, which resulted positive definite. Indeed, with α equal to 0.05 or
8 0.10, the smallest singular values were higher than 0 (respectively, $1.8e-5$ and $2.0e-5$).

9 **Discussion**

10 The X-chromosome genetic relationship matrix (\mathbf{G}^X) allows to perform genetic studies such as
11 the estimation of its contribution to phenotypic or genetic variation. Several studies suggested
12 that this contribution might be large for certain traits, e.g. [10–12]. Similarly, this GRM could
13 be used to improve genomic predictions when this chromosome contributes significantly to
14 the trait. X-specific relationships might also be useful in studies of relationships in the wild.
15 Since expected relationships for the X-chromosome are different compared to those for
16 autosomes, they provide additional information to determine relatedness between individuals.
17 However, here, we have illustrated that the use of \mathbf{G}^X is not trivial because individuals sharing
18 their entire X-specific chromosome are relatively frequent since males carry only one copy
19 and transmit it without recombination. As a result, \mathbf{G}^X might be regularly non-positive definite
20 (depending on the sample) and consequently non invertible, thus causing computational
21 problems. Overall, we observed that the X-chromosome (X-specific part) has a lower
22 dimensionality. This is consistent with the smaller number of chromosomes in the sample and
23 is expected since certain relationships are estimated between individuals that have a single
24 chromosome (we observed more extreme relationships between males). In species with a

1 balanced sex-ratio, the effective population size (N_e) for the X-chromosome is also smaller, $\frac{3}{4}$
2 of the autosomal N_e [39]. However, when the number of males is much smaller than the
3 number of females, N_e can be slightly larger for the X-chromosome than for the autosomes
4 [15, 40]. The lower dimensionality is also related to the reduced recombination rate on the X-
5 chromosome (male chromosomes are transmitted without recombination) resulting in less
6 shuffling and higher LD levels, e.g. [15, 41]. More generally, the level of diversity is also
7 lower on the X-chromosome [39].

8 To address numerical problems associated with reduced dimensionality, statistical methods
9 known as “bending” can be applied to render \mathbf{G}^X positive definite. \mathbf{G}^X can be bended using an
10 identity matrix but the use of \mathbf{S} might better preserve the genetic relationships. Indeed, we
11 illustrated that for markers on the X-specific part, \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{G}^X have similar expectations and,
12 thus, can be combined. In particular, the heritability of gene content obtained with \mathbf{S}
13 confirmed this point. We also showed that for markers on the PAR, expectations are different
14 and that \mathbf{P}^r had similar expectations to \mathbf{G} for these markers. Combination of \mathbf{G}^X and \mathbf{S} (or
15 eventually \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{P}^r for the PAR) would not only be useful for bending purposes, it would
16 also allow to combine genotyped and ungenotyped individuals as for the prediction of gene
17 content for a locus with a major effect [24, 25] or in the single-step GBLUP context. This
18 merging of genotyped and ungenotyped individuals might be useful for both genomic
19 predictions [2, 3] and association studies [4] on the X-chromosome. In the case of such a
20 GWAS relying on GBLUP or SSGBLUP, we recommend the use of \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{G}^X (or \mathbf{P}^r and \mathbf{G})
21 rather than \mathbf{A} or \mathbf{G} , as done in previous studies [42].

22 However, several algorithms can be considered to estimate \mathbf{G}^X . Here, we used an algorithm
23 similar to the first method proposed by VanRaden [20]. We obtained similar observations
24 when the relationships were estimated using the rules proposed by Amin et al. [43] (also

1 known as VanRaden second method), giving more weight to rare alleles. Alternatively, a
2 similarity matrix, e.g. [44, 45] can be obtained using the same allele frequency for all SNPs
3 (0.5). Interestingly, with such an approach, the diagonal elements for males would all be equal
4 to 0.5 as for \mathbf{S} , whereas deviations, sometimes large, are observed with the two other
5 approaches. In addition, this approach is in line with the use of metafounders as presented in
6 the Theory section.

7 As previously mentioned, when a SSGBLUP is considered, good compatibility of \mathbf{G}^X and \mathbf{S} is
8 required. In addition, it is likely that different origins (male population and female population,
9 perhaps evolving over years or origins as in genetic groups) need to be modelled. A solution
10 for both problems is the use of metafounders [21], for which \mathbf{G}^X is simply obtained by setting
11 allele frequencies to 0.5 and \mathbf{S} is obtained by fitting male and female metafounders (as many
12 pairs as the number of genetic groups considered), and rules for \mathbf{S} and its inverse \mathbf{S}^{-1} are a
13 simple modification of Fernando and Grossman [16] as illustrated in the Julia code provided
14 in Additional file 4.

15 Importantly, we observed that \mathbf{G}^X deviates from its expectations \mathbf{S} , more than \mathbf{G} from \mathbf{A} . \mathbf{S} is
16 therefore not a perfect predictor of \mathbf{G}^X and it is consequently important to use realized
17 relationships for the X-chromosome as much as possible in applications including genomic
18 predictions or genetic variance partitioning. However, as we mentioned earlier, bending
19 techniques are required and might result in a loss of information. For these reasons, the best
20 strategy might be a SNP-BLUP on the X-chromosome or a single-step method that does not
21 require bending, in the spirit of Fernando et al. [26].

22 Certain aspects related to the use of the X-chromosome in genomic applications were not
23 investigated in the current study. For instance, we expressed additive genetic effects either on

1 performances of daughters, or on own performances. However, additive genetic effects can be
2 expressed also on other scales. For instance, genetic effects transmitted by sires to their
3 daughters are different from genetic effects transmitted to their sons. Therefore, different
4 prediction transmitting abilities might be proposed. VanRaden et al. [6] give more details on
5 these aspects in the context of genomic evaluation in dairy cattle. Genotypes on the X-
6 chromosome require also specific phasing, e.g. [46, 47] or imputation strategies [47–49].

7 **Conclusions**

8 The X-chromosome has often been ignored although it might have important contributions to
9 the genetic variation of complex traits. Certain genomic applications that combine genotyped
10 and ungenotyped individuals require the combination of pedigree-based and realized
11 relationship matrices. For markers on the X-chromosome, specific rules have been developed
12 for both matrices (respectively \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{G}^X). In our study, we proposed to estimate dosage
13 compensation using multiple-trait models instead of assuming a predefined value. Then, we
14 showed theoretically and empirically that both relationship matrices have the same
15 expectations. Therefore, we recommend combining \mathbf{G}^X with \mathbf{S} in applications related to gene
16 content or in SSGBLUP approaches. We also observed that realized relationships present
17 strong levels of variation around expected values and \mathbf{S} is hence not a perfect predictor of \mathbf{G}^X .
18 In addition, many individuals share entire chromosomes and have relationships close to 1.
19 Thus, for markers on the X-chromosome, a SNP-BLUP strategy might be a good strategy
20 since it relies on the realized relationships while having less numerical problems than a
21 GBLUP relying on the GRM.

22 **Declarations**

23 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

1 Not applicable

2 **Consent for publication**

3 Not applicable

4 **Data availability**

5 The data that support the findings of this study (genotypes) belong to third parties (INRAE
6 and Alice). Restrictions apply to the availability of these data that are not publicly available.

7 The authors can be contacted for a reasonable request and with permission of data owners.

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1 **Authors' contributions**

2 TD and AL conceived the study, interpreted the results and wrote the manuscript. AL wrote
3 the Theory section with help from TD, who added the note for markers on the PAR. TD
4 analyzed data with help from AL. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

5 **Competing interests**

6 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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1 **Figures**

2 **Figure 1 Comparison of expected and realized correlations between additive genetic**
3 **effects estimated on chromosome-X (a, d), whole-genome (b, e) and for the chromosome**
4 **2 (c, f).**

5 Right panels (d, e and f) were obtained using relationships among males only. A hexbin
6 function was used with a 200×200 grid. The color scale indicates the number of relationships
7 having a given value.

8 **Figure 2 Distribution of genomic correlations estimated with markers on the X-**
9 **chromosome (left panel), on the 29 autosomes (center) or on chromosome 2 (right**
10 **panel).**

11 Relationships were estimated for sire/sons relationships (top), full-sisters (center) and paternal
12 half-sisters (bottom).

13 **Figure 3 Heritability of the gene content along the X-chromosome (X-specific part).**

14 **(a) For all genotyped individuals**

15 **(b) For genotyped males only.**

16 Black and gray dots indicate heritabilities estimated with the pedigree-based relationships
17 using rules specific to the X-chromosome (**S**) and general rules for the autosomes (**A**),
18 respectively.

19 **Figure 4 Illustration of the sex-gradient for markers in the pseudo-autosomal region**
20 **(PAR).**

21 The probability for offspring to inherit the paternal haplotype from their parent has been
22 estimated with LINKPHASE3. These probabilities are plotted for transmission from sires to
23 son (blue) and daughters (red) and from dams to sons (dashed black) and daughters (gray).

24 **Figure 5 Heritability of the gene content for markers in the pseudo-autosomal region**
25 **(PAR).**

26 Heritabilities were estimated with the different expected relationship matrices including **S**
27 (sex-specific rules), **A** (autosomes) and expected relationships for markers from the PAR
28 located at r cM from the pseudo-autosomal boundary (PAB).

29

1 Tables

2 **Table 1 Expected (pedigree-based) additive genetic relationships on the autosomes and**
 3 **on the X-chromosome (specific part) for different categories of animals**

Relationship class	Autosomes		X-Chromosome	
	Relationships	Correlations	Relationships	Correlations
Sire / son	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.00
Sire / daughter	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.71
Dam / son	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.71
Dam / daughter	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
Paternal half-sibs (two males)	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.00
Paternal half-sibs (male/female)	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.00
Paternal half-sibs (two females)	0.25	0.25	0.50	0.50
Maternal half-sibs (two males)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.50
Maternal half-sibs (male/female)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.35
Maternal half-sibs (two females)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Full-sibs (two males)	0.50	0.50	0.25	0.50
Full-sibs (male / female)	0.50	0.50	0.25	0.35
Full-sibs (two females)	0.50	0.50	0.75	0.75
Diagonal elements (males)	1.00	1.00	0.50	1.00
Diagonal elements (females)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

4 The relationships are also represented in terms of correlations (i.e., dividing by the square root of 0.5 for each
 5 male involved in the relationship)
 6

1 **Table 2 Comparison of average realized (marker-based) and expected (pedigree-based)**
2 **additive genetic relationships on the X-chromosome (specific part), on all autosomes and**
3 **on chromosome 2 for different categories of animals. Relationships are expressed as**
4 **correlations**

Relationship class	Chromosome X		All autosomes		Chromosome 2	
	Pedigree	Genomic	Pedigree	Genomic	Pedigree	Genomic
Sire/son	0.031	-0.027	0.541	0.482	0.541	0.470
Sire/daughter	0.721	0.697	0.543	0.482	0.543	0.474
Dam/son	0.721	0.700	0.545	0.481	0.545	0.462
Dam/daughter	0.539	0.479	0.545	0.484	0.545	0.476
Paternal half-sibs (two males)	0.066	0.038	0.324	0.230	0.324	0.218
Paternal half-sibs (male/female)	0.064	-0.021	0.324	0.225	0.324	0.207
Paternal half-sibs (two females)	0.546	0.479	0.322	0.226	0.322	0.208
Maternal half-sibs (two males)	0.522	0.523	0.318	0.229	0.318	0.175
Maternal half-sibs (male/female)	0.387	0.339	0.321	0.229	0.321	0.210
Maternal half-sibs (two females)	0.309	0.228	0.321	0.232	0.321	0.222
Full-sibs (two males)	0.510	0.416	0.544	0.476	0.544	0.510
Full-sibs (male/female)	0.383	0.315	0.546	0.477	0.546	0.446
Full-sibs (two females)	0.768	0.734	0.542	0.482	0.542	0.473
Diagonal elements (males)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Diagonal elements (females)	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

5

1 **Table 3 Dimensionality of different genomic relationship matrices**

Statistic	X-chromosome	BTA2	Autosomes
Number of positive SV	5921	5693	6085
Number of SV accounting for 90% of total	15	24	105
Number of SV accounting for 95% of total	25	39	250
Number of SV accounting for 99% of total	53	85	793
Number of SV accounting for 99.9% of total	122	191	1977
Proportion of correlations > 0.90	1.0e-4	1.7e-6	1.1e-7
Proportion of correlations > 0.95	5.4e-5	5.4e-7	1.1e-7
Proportion of correlations > 0.99	3.4e-5	2.7e-7	1.1e-7
Proportion of correlations > 0.90 (males only)	1.6e-3	4.9e-6	0
Proportion of correlations > 0.95 (males only)	1.1e-3	0	0
Proportion of correlations > 0.99 (males only)	8.9e-4	0	0

2 The dimensionality was assessed based on the singular value decomposition (SVD). The frequency of high
3 genomic correlations between individuals are also indicated (either in the entire genotyped samples, either in
4 genotyped males only).
5

1 **Additional files**

2 **Additional file 1**

3 Format: pdf

4 Title: Metafounder's theory as applied to the **S** matrix, rules and code for this matrix and its
5 inverse

6 **Additional file 2 Table S1**

7 Format: pdf

8 Title: Comparison of realized (marker-based) and expected (pedigree-based) additive genetic
9 relationships on the X-chromosome (specific part) for different categories of animals

10 **Additional file 2 Table S2**

11 Format: pdf

12 Title: Comparison of realized (marker-based) and expected (pedigree-based) additive genetic
13 relationships on the autosomes (all together) for different categories of animals

14 **Additional file 2 Table S3**

15 Format: pdf

16 Title: Comparison of realized (marker-based) and expected (pedigree-based) additive genetic
17 relationships on the BTA2 for different categories of animals

18 **Additional file 3 Figure S1**

19 Format: pdf

20 Title: Heritability of the gene content along the X-chromosome (X-specific part), when males
21 considered homozygous are coded as {0,2}. A. For all genotyped individuals, B. For
22 genotyped males only. Black and gray dots indicate heritabilities estimated with the pedigree-
23 based relationships using rules specific to the X-chromosome (**S**) and general rules for the
24 autosomes (**A**), respectively.

25 **Additional file 4**

26 Format: jl

27 Title: Julia code